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Research and Innovation Framework Program

CHESSETUP

Deliverable 5.2 PILOT EXPERIENCES

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Pilot Experiences

1. Introduction

The aim of this report is to provide the evidences of the construction progress for the three pilot experiences:

- Lavola Pilot
- Sant Cugat Pilot
- Corby Pilot

Progress reports for each of the sites have been done during the implementation phase. They are collected in this document. These reports state the tasks performed during the period, the incidents encountered, the causes of the delays and other relevant observations noted as well as a photographic collection to show the progress of the works.

Following is the calendar of works for each of the Pilots.

Deliverable 5.2

Sant Cugat Pilot calendar

Activity	Month	Dec'18	Jan'19	Feb'19	Mar'19	Apr'19	May'19	Jun'19	Jul'19	Total
	Project Month	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	
Previous works and measures	Scheduled									100 %
	Accomplished									100%
Roof reinforce and new structure	Scheduled									100%
	Accomplished									100%
Tank construction	Scheduled									100%
	Accomplished									100%
PV-T Panels Installations	Scheduled									100%
	Accomplished									100%
Hydraulic Installations	Scheduled									100%
	Accomplished									100%
Elec/monitoring installation	Scheduled									100%
	Accomplished									100%
Final works	Scheduled									100%
	Accomplished									70%

Deliverable 5.2

Corby Pilot calendar

2. Lavola Pilot Progress Report

Following is the activity summary of the implementation of the Lavola Pilot.

2.1. Progress report from 1st to 15th May 2018

Tasks performed

On 23rd March the City Council issued the permits for the works in the Ecobuilding.

On 27th April the contract with the photovoltaic supplier was signed.

On 4th June construction tasks will start.

Incidents / delays

Photovoltaic installation works will start on June instead of March as it states de calendar. However, the contractor has committed it will be finished by July.

It is still not signed the contract with the supplier of monitoring and control and auxiliary-related tasks.

There is no specific data yet from the heat pump that Ulster will provide (specially related to size and weight to proceed with proper works). However, the partner committed that Lavola will have the Heat Pump ready to install in Manlleu the 15th July.

Other observations

There are not observations to be mentioned

Photographs of the works

There are no pictures available because the works have not been started.

2.2. Progress report from 1st to 15th June 2018

Tasks performed

The Lavola's pilot construction works started on 4th June construction tasks will start.

The following are the tasks carried out during this period:

- Replacement of the roof cantilever to identify the structural pillars of the building and check the status of the water insulation layer.
- Marking the position of the metallic structure of the PV array.
- Preparation of the hydraulic installation of the new heat pump.
- Relocation of the current solar thermal panels.

Incidents / delays

There were adverse weather conditions of the first week with heavy rains almost every day that slowed down the works on the roof.

Other observations

There are not observations to be mentioned

Photographs of the works

4th June

Images of the rooftop before the starting of the works:

5-6th June

Images of the cantilever replacement and the metallic structure of the PV array position marking.

8th June

Images of the installation of the hydraulic conducts for the new heat pump.

11th June

Images of the installations of the hydraulic conducts for the new heat pump.

14th June

Images of the installations of the hydraulic conducts of the new heat pump and images of the relocation of the current solar thermal panels.

2.3. Progress report from 1st to 20th July 2018

Tasks performed

The following are the tasks carried out during the period compressed from 5th July 20th July:

- Replacement of the solar panels
- Replacement of the solar trackers
- Electrical and control wires
- Building the concrete slab for the heat pump

Incidents / delays

There was a slight rethinking of the metallic structure of the photovoltaic installation that delayed its installation on this week. It is planned to execute it next week.

Other observations

Works are planned to be finished by 31st of July, except the installation of the heat pump and the monitoring and control system.

Photographs of the works

5th July

Images of panel's replacement works:

Images after the solar panels' replacement:

Images of the electrical and control wires installation:

19th July

Images of the solar tracker replacement:

2.4. Progress report from 20th to 30th July 2018

Tasks performed

The following are the tasks carried out during the period compressed from 21st July 30th July:

- Assemblage of the metallic structure
- Installation of solar photovoltaic panels

Incidents / delays

There was a delay of the structure assembly because of the holiday period of the supplier.

Works related to the photovoltaic installation were planned to be finished by 31st of July. However, the delay of the supplier and after that the holiday period of the company, it is expected to be finished by the end of August.

Other observations

The installation of the heat pump and the monitoring and control system depends on the answer of the Commission.

Photographs of the works

27th July

Images of structure assemblage:

30th July

2.5. Progress report from 1st to 31st August 2018

Tasks performed

The following are the tasks carried out during the period compressed from 1st to 31st August:

- Installation of solar photovoltaic panels

Incidents / delays

The installation of the heat pump and the monitoring and control system depends on the answer of the Commission.

Other observations

There are not observations to be mentioned

Photographs of the works

Images of the solar panels installation:

3rd August

20th August

24th August

2.6. Progress report from December 2018 to April 2019

Tasks performed

The following are the tasks carried out during the period compressed from December 2018 to April 2019:

- After the approval by the Agency to acquire a commercial heat pump with the Ulster University funds, we work to determine which of the commercial heat pump offered by the makes, together with Ulster University, was the most suitable for the pilot.
- Comparing the results of the data sheets and Ulster University analysis, we select the heat pump of Carrier and make the order of purchase.
- Start the adequation and installation of the sensors and control wire for the new control system.

Incidents / delays

- Carrier did not have heat pumps available in stock, so it must be manufactured, and the delivery period is 6 weeks. Thus, we will receive the heat pump in mid-May.
- Thermal meters must be changed from the designed in the original project due to a different diameter between the previous design and the ones the heat pump need.

Other observations

The monitoring and control system finalization will depend on the reception of the thermal meters.

Photographs of the works

Images of the adequation and installation of the sensors and control wire for the new control system.

Control boards implementation

Sensors implementation

Renewable energy control and registration

2.7. Progress report from May to July 2019

Tasks performed

The following are the tasks carried out during the period compressed from May 2019 to mid-July 2019:

- 15th May, reception and installation of the heat pump
- Finalizing the connection of the heat pump pipes to the circuit
- Installing the control elements (temperature sensors, heat meter, electric meter)
- 2nd July, official commissioning of the heat pump by Carrier
- Installation of the control system software
- Turn on the heat pump to cool the building
- Adjustment of the set points and operation schemes
- Following up the proper operation of the equipment and the control system

Incidents / delays

- Heat Pump was installed on 15th May. It could not be commissioned since control elements were completely installed and pass the inspection of the manufacturer. However, during this period, there was no need for cooling the building. So, in case it was ready to be used, it would not be operated because the building did not have cooling demand since the end of June – beginning of July.
- 21th June an electrical power cut was planned, after the workday to not interfere the normal office user's activity, to connect the heat pump to the internal net.
- Carrier plan the commissioning tasks on the 2nd July.
- The control software was also installed the 2nd of July. However, it was not finished. It remains the integration of the meters.
- Turn on the heat pump for cooling the building.
- Regulate the temperature and control signals of the building to its best operation.
- It was notice that the first floor was over cooled. During the week starting on 15th July it was found that a piece of weld spatter was remain into the circuit and block the valve. Maintenance service review the system to detect it and disassembly the valve to remove the waste that avoid that valve could close 100%.
- The 23th July heat pump was stopped because of lack of pressure. It could be happened because of the tasks of the first-floor valve problem.
- It is pending the integration of the meters to the control software.

Other observations

-

Photographs of the works

Heat Pump and tank installation

Sensor installation

Meters

Control system

CONTROL BOMBA CALOR

Control: ON

Alarma: NO Permis: SI
Avis: NO Demanda: SI
 Marxa: SI

Temperatura Impulsió: 9.1°C
Temperatura Retorn: 11.2°C
Temperatura Acumulador: 9.3°C

Sortida Válvules: SI Válvula Impulsió en Posició: SI
Sortida Bomba Calor: SI Válvula Retorn en Posició: SI
 Senyal Fluxostat: SI

CONTROL CLIMATITZADOR

Control: ON
Marxa: ON

Permis: SI
Alarma: NO Demanda: SI
 En Marxa: SI

Condició en Froid: SI
Condició en Calor: SI

Controlador

Tipus	Valor	Unitat	Unitat
Temperatura	9.1	°C	SI
Temperatura	11.2	°C	SI
Temperatura	9.3	°C	SI

2023-12-15 10:00

2.8. Progress report from August to September 2019

Tasks performed

The following are the tasks carried out during the period compressed from August 2019 to September 2019:

- Following up the proper operation of the equipment and the control system, as well as the adjustments of the set points and operation schemes
- Updating some screens of the control system software
- Integration of the meters to the control system software
- Analyze the data from the sensors and meters
- Solve some issues regarding the heat pump operation (it was stopped 3 times due to electrical failures)

Incidents / delays

- Data from the registers must be deputed because it shows the energy consumed by the system analyzed plus other residual measures that are generated automatically and disturbs the real energy consumption.
- Thermal energy meter is implemented in the software. We can control the instantaneous energy consumption as well as the flow. However, it must be checked (verify it is reading correctly) and integrate it with the other electric meter in order to allow download the data recorded.
- Heat pump was stopped 3 times since it was commissioned. The problems were related to the electrical voltage. When it turned off, the old chiller was automatically switched on. So, during this period both heat pumps and chiller were working alternatively. This issue was reported to Carrier.

Other observations

-

Photographs of the works

Update the screen of the control software

A main screen was implemented in the control software in which there are information regarding the state of the and control the lighting (exterior and interior patio), fans, movable louvers and the glasshouse)

A screen to monitor and download the data of the energy meters was implemented.

Data inici: 2019-08-13 Data final: 2019-08-13

August 2019

Mo Tu We Th Fr Sa Su

1 2 3 4
5 6 7 8 9 10 11
12 13 14 15 16 17 18
19 20 21 22 23 24 25
26 27 28 29 30 31

Calor Bomba Calor Residual

Gràfic d'Energia Reactiva

Enviar

Consums

Descarregar Resum

A concrete period can be selected to download data to analyse the energy consumption

Data inici: 2019-08-13 Data final: 2019-08-13

Marcar Tots / Desmarcar Tots

General
 Parciais
 Força
 Planta Refredadora
 SAI
 Enlluminat
 Aigua
 Gràfic d'Energia Activa

Bomba Calor Residual
 Bomba Calor
 FV
 Fotovoltaica
 CDDP
 Gràfic d'Energia Reactiva

Enviar

Consums

Descarregar Resum

Meters can analysed globally or we can select which do we want to study.

Taula resum d'energia activa [kWh]

Parciais

	P1	P2	P3	# Interp.	Total mesurat:	Factor	Total Estimad.	Percentatge
Total	20	82	68	0	170	1,00	170	118,83 %

General

	P1	P2	P3	# Interp.	Total mesurat:	Factor	Total Estimad.	Percentatge
General	7	68	68	0	143	1,00	143	100,00 %

* Si el factor és diferent a 1,00, s'està aplicant aquest factor de correcció al total mesurat

Descarregar corba:

Quart-horària | Horària

After the selection of the period willing to study and the meters to include in it, the software shows a summary table and a graph with the energy consumption.

Corba de càrrega								
A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1	Corba de càrrega							
2								
3	Client	LAVOLA						
4	Tarifa	3.0A						
5	Data corba	30/09/2019						
6	Període co	13/08/2019	13/08/2019					
7	Energia	Reactiva (kVALh)						
8	Tipus de cor	Diària						
9								
10	Etiqueta	Esclau	Data	Hora	Energia	Període	# Interp.	
11	Parcials	SAI	13/08/2019	0:00:00	0	2	0	
12	Parcials	Enllumenat	13/08/2019	0:00:00	0,12	2	0	
13	Parcials	Total	13/08/2019	0:00:00	0,12	2	0	
14	Bomba Calor	Residual	13/08/2019	0:00:00	0	2	0	
15	Bomba Calor	Bomba Calor	13/08/2019	0:00:00	0	2	0	
16	FV	Fotovoltaica	13/08/2019	0:00:00	0,01	2	0	
17	FV	Total	13/08/2019	0:00:00	0,01	2	0	
18	General	Residual	13/08/2019	0:00:00	49	2	0	
19	General	General	13/08/2019	0:00:00	49	2	0	
20	Residual	Residual Me	13/08/2019	0:00:00	0	2	0	
21	Residual	Residual No	13/08/2019	0:00:00	48,87	2	0	
22	Residual	Total	13/08/2019	0:00:00	48,87	2	0	
23								
24								
25								
26								

An Excel Sheet is generated with the data selected. I can be 15 minutes, hourly or daily register.

The thermal energy meter has also been integrated in the software.

3. Sant Cugat Pilot Progress Report

Following is the activity summary of the implementation of the Sant Cugat Pilot.

3.1. April 2018 progress report

Tasks performed

The bids evaluation phase has been ended and the contract adjudication phase has been started. It is expected to sign the contract with the construction company last week of May.

Despite of the contract has been not signed, the company that has awarded the public tender is known and published, so first meeting with the construction company and the coordinator technician has been done.

Once the contract has been signed, the first construction tasks will start.

Incidents / delays

There is not incidents and delays to be mentioned. The works will begin as was scheduled.

Other observations

There are not observations to be mentioned

Photographs of the works

Because the works have not been initiated, there is not pictures to include at the report.

3.2. May 2018 progress report

Tasks performed

The City Council, in accordance with the law, has requested more information from the construction company. This fact has delayed the signing of the contract. It is expected to be signed in two weeks once the award is officially published.

Although the contract has not been signed, a second meeting was held with the construction company, the work coordinator and the outsourced company that manages the Sports Center.

The aim of the meeting was to coordinate the construction phase with the uses and needs of the center along the summer. Next week the scheduled work will be redefined.

Incidents / delays

The signature of the contract has been delayed two weeks. Therefore, the start of the works has been delayed two weeks as well.

Other observations

There are not observations to be mentioned.

Photographs of the works

Because the works have not been initiated, there is not pictures to include at the report.

3.3. November 2018 progress report

Tasks performed

- Roof reinforce and structure

The high weight of the hybrid panels together with the new regulation in relation to the wooden structures, has obliged to perform an expensive reinforcement of said structure. As of today, this reinforcement has been done.

At the same time, drilling has also been carried out on the roof to be able to make the anchors with the benches of the panels. The process has been long and tedious, working at the same time one operator on the roof and another inside the pavilion by means of a lifting crane. It is planned to install the first benches during the first fortnight of the month of December.

In parallel, in the workshop, the manufacturer is making the structure in which the panels will rest.

- Tank construction

The shape of the tank has been modified with respect to that designed in the project. This will be cylindrical instead of rectangular. The reasons that have led to this modification have been constructive reasons (easier to build) and less energy losses.

With the premise of maintaining the same storage volume, the height of the tank has increased because its new shape. Due to the height limitations of the site, it has been decided to reduce the insulation widths at the top and bottom (100 mm - 400 mm of rock wool). In order that this reduction of insulation does not result in an increase in energy losses, a closure of the deposit has been planned by the construction of a wall of concrete blocks and the injection of hot air from the pump room annexed to the TEST.

During the excavation process to build the structural foundations, an asbestos cement pipe has been located next to the works. Obviously, this has led to a reduction in the productive performance of the excavation since it was done manually without machinery so as not to damage the localized pipe and to keep a safety place.

Parallel to these activities, the deposit has begun to be built in the workshop. This deposit will be manufactured by rings 2.8 m high and 1.5 m wide. Once in

the work, the assembly of the rings will be carried out by means of welding. The arrival of the first rings is expected at the 3rd week of December.

- PV-T panels installation

Although the installation of the hybrid panels cannot be started since their benches are not placed, the panels are already in the works.

The metal support structure of the panels is scheduled to begin installation in mid-December

- Hydraulic installation

This task has begun with the installation of the pumping groups of the system, the valves and their collectors.

The elements of the installation are built in the workshop and are assembled by welding on site, the exchanger has been received on site and the heat pump and the inertia tank have already been ordered from the manufacturers waiting for their reception.

The hydraulic installation is one of the tasks that will end later because it depends on the completion of the other tasks.

- Elect. And monitoring installation

Like the hydraulic installation, the electrical installation has started in the workshop (electrical and communication cabinet) and it will not be able to finish until the rest of the tasks are completed.

The wire trays have been installed between the control computer and the rooms where the sensor and control elements are located and between the electrical cabinet and the supply points.

Contacts have been initiated with the electricity supplier company for the legalization of the self-consumption installation, but no definitive answer has yet been obtained.

Incidents / delays

- The modification of the form and material of the tank, the cement pipe of asbestos that has been found in the foundations of the tank and problems related to the safety equipment that to use in the roof of the building have entailed the continuous change of the plan of security.

Each modification has carried out an approval by the City Council. This procedure needs time in a public administration (2 weeks), so it has delayed the original construction plan.

- The asbestos cement pipeline, in addition to the above, has also caused a reduction in work performance in accordance with the safety plan.
- The time used for the design of the new tank and its validation has also caused a delay to be considered.

Other observations

The uncertainty of the law of Spanish electric self-consumption, the particularity of self-consumption in a medium voltage supply installation and the dependence on the response of the electric power company make it feared that the set-up may be delayed.

With the aim of reducing this risk, the City Council insists weekly on a response from the supplier company.

Photographs of the works

- Roof reinforce and structure

Pavilion roof before intervention

Pavilion roof after intervention (anchors for branches)

Reinforce of the wooden structure

Reinforce of the wooden structure

- Tank construction

Asbestos cement pipe

Asbestos cement pipe

Piling and drilling rig machine

Foundations of the TEST

Foundations of the TEST

- PV-T panels installation

Hybrid panels on site

- Hydraulic installation

Pump groups and collectors

Pump groups and collectors

3.4. December 2018 progress report

Tasks performed

- Roof reinforce and structure

The task of reinforcement of the roof and the task of installing the structure of the panels have been finalized during the month of December, two weeks before as planned.

- Tank construction

Despite the existence of an asbestos pipe, the reinforcement of the pavement where the tank will be built has been made through a set of piles and a concrete slab.

The extreme covers of the tank have arrived at the work. Throughout the month of January, all the rings to be welded are expected to arrive. The rings measure 1.8 m in diameter and it has become a physical restriction on how to take those rings to the place where they will be assembled. A window of a courtyard has had to be disassembled and a corner of a wall has been demolished to guarantee the access of the ring. Obviously, both will be rebuilt at the end of this task.

Next steps of this task will be to assemble the rings, to insulate the tank, to build the closure of the tank and to connect the tank with the hydraulic system and the electrical and monitoring installation.

- PV-T panels installation

The metal support structure of the panels has been anchored to the roof. As a test, one bench and its respective set of panels have also been installed. Once the test has given positive results, the rest of the benches and panels will be installed in January.

The process to bring the structure, benches and panels to the roof has been carried out through a mobile crane placed on the street. Because the road will be closed during the Christmas holidays, when mobility is lower compared to the rest of the year, it is not expected to produce a significant bottleneck.

Following step after the panel's installation will be to install the footbridge and the ladder needed to access to the roof for future maintenance tasks.

The connection to the hydraulic system and to the electrical and monitoring installation will be made in the first fortnight of the month of February.

- Hydraulic installation

As is explained above, the hydraulic installation must be implemented in parallel of the rest of the task when they are about the end.

The main elements of the system (valves, pumping groups and some collectors) have been installed. A leak test of those collectors has been started; the results of the test will be known at the second week of January.

Whole task is planned to end at the last week of February.

- Elect. And monitoring installation

Like the hydraulic installation, the electrical and monitoring installation will finish once the rest of the tasks are completed.

Contacts have been initiated with the electricity supplier company for the legalization of the self-consumption installation, but no definitive answer has yet been obtained.

Incidents / delays

Along December there wasn't any incident and/or delay to be mentioned. Following, you can see what incidents and delays were reported last month.

- The modification of the form and material of the tank, the cement pipe of asbestos that has been found in the foundations of the tank and problems related to the safety equipment that to use in the roof of the building have entailed the continuous change of the plan of security.

Each modification has carried out an approval by the City Council. This procedure needs time in a public administration (2 weeks), so it has delayed the original construction plan.

- The asbestos cement pipeline, in addition to the above, has also caused a reduction in work performance in accordance with the safety plan.
- The time used for the design of the new tank and its validation has also caused a delay to be considered.

Other observations

The uncertainty of the law of Spanish electric self-consumption, the particularity of self-consumption in a medium voltage supply installation and the dependence on the response of the electric power company make it feared that the set-up may be delayed.

With the aim of reducing this risk, the City Council insists weekly on a response from the supplier company.

Photographs of the works

- Roof reinforce and structure

Panels structure installation process

Panels structure installation process

Panels structures installed on December

- Tank construction

Concrete slab for TEST

Extreme covers of the TEST

Auxiliary gadgets needed to bring the TEST rings

Corner demolished to guarantee the access of the TEST rings to the place

- PV-T panels installation

First panels installed

- Hydraulic installation

Pump groups and collectors

3.5. January 2019 progress report

Tasks performed

- Roof reinforce and structure

100% Accomplished.

- Tank construction

At the end of January, all the TEST rings have arrived at the site and 75% of them have been assembled.

The next steps of this task will be to assemble the rest of the rings, isolate the tank, build the tank closure and connect the tank with the hydraulic system and the electrical and monitoring installation.

The task has been delayed and is expected to end in the second half of March. The redesign of the shape of the tank during the works also involves a new design of the connection of the hydraulic installation and control and monitoring. This new technical design has been causing for delay.

- PV-T panels installation

All benches and panels of the roof have been installed. The footbridge is 80% installed, only first footbridge with the safety railing for maintenance is waiting to be installed.

The connection to the hydraulic system and to the electrical and monitoring installation as well has been carried out. Only final works regarding the hydraulic, electrical and monitoring are pending but those works are included in other tasks.

Following step will be to install the ladder needed to access to the roof for future maintenance tasks and the final works.

The task has been delayed due to the construction validation of the ladder and the safety railing for maintenance.

- Hydraulic installation

Although the hydraulic installation can be carried out in parallel with the rest of the tasks, it cannot be finished since the other tasks have not been completed.

As explained above, some tasks have been delayed and, consequently, this task too. The connection to the tank has been redesigned due to the new shape of the TEST and due to the constraints of the space available in the corridor where the TEST has been built.

The main hydraulic elements (valves, pumps and heat exchangers) have already been installed.

The end of the task is expected to end at the end of March.

- Elect. And monitoring installation

Once again, the electrical and monitoring installation will end once the rest of the tasks are completed. The wiring to the elements of the CHESSE SETUP system has been completed and it is waiting to receive the electrical panel and its connection to the elements.

The electricity supplier company has received our connection request and they have contacted us. During the month of February, it is expected to hold a meeting with the technician of the electricity supplier company.

The end of the task is expected to end at the end of March.

Incidents / delays

The progress of the construction phase throughout this month has not been as expected. Some tasks have been delayed because the TEST has been completely redesigned from the original Project.

The new design has taken time, but it has not been the only one in the entire process. Once designed, the construction company must budget the new proposal with its manufacturers and suppliers and finally be validated again by the Works Coordinator.

In addition to this, the new regulation of the public contract with a new tedious and complex administrative procedure has forced to approve a new project with its modifications. As a result, all the expenses certified by the construction company could not be approved by the City Council of Sant Cugat while the approval process has not been completed. This financial stress for the construction company has created an uncomfortable environment and has a negative influence on the performance of the works. During February, more modifications could appear, but no more delays are expected.

At this point, it is important to mention that the planning of the project cannot be further delayed. In that case, the monitoring system programmed by Wattia would be at risk of doing it out of time.

From the Town Hall of Sant Cugat, in order to face this unwanted risk, all possible efforts are being made to comply with the planned objectives and it has increased control and monitoring of the works.

Other observations

The uncertainty of the law of Spanish electric self-consumption, the particularity of self-consumption in a medium voltage supply installation and the dependence on the response of the electric power company make it feared that the set-up for the electrical production may be delayed.

A meeting with the technician of the electricity supplier company on February is scheduled.

Photographs of the works

- Roof reinforce and structure

Panels structure

- Tank construction

TEST

TEST

TEST rings

- PV-T panels installation

Hybrid panels installed

Hybrid panels and footbridge

- Hydraulic installation

Hydraulic collectors

Hydraulic collectors

Heat exchanger and electrical wired

Electrical wired

3.6. March 2019 progress report

Tasks performed

- Roof reinforce and structure (100 % Accomplished)

The final works included in this task are the sealing tests of the roof and the replacement of the air conditioning ducts removed at the beginning of the works. Both works have started, and they will be finished on April.

- Tank construction (96 % Accomplished)

The TEST has been mounted and connected to the hydraulic system. Tank insulation has begun and will be completed during the first week of April. At the same time, the deposit is being filled to perform the sealing tests.

Once the insulation has been completed and the seal verified, the task will be completed until the final works are completed. The enclosure of the tank room is included in these final works. It has been considered that before its execution and to facilitate the start-up phase, it will be necessary to delay this task at the end of the project once its correct operation of the TEST is verified.

- PV-T panels installation (100% Accomplished)

Banks and panels have been installed and connected to the electrical and hydraulic systems. The ladder to access the roof has also been installed.

The task will be completed once the footbridge of the first bank line has been installed. It is expected to end during the third week of April.

- Hydraulic installation (89% Accomplished)

All elements of the system have been connected hydraulically and the sealing tests of the pipes have been carried out with satisfactory results. The installation of the power dissipater is pending. Its installation is expected during the month of April.

The insulation of the pipes has started. This work will be included in the task of final works.

- Elect. And monitoring installation (84% Accomplished)

The electrical panels have already been installed on site. Most of the connections to CHESS SETUP system elements have also been made. The rest

of the electrical and monitoring connections and the connection to the sports center are pending. The forecast is that this task will end during the second fortnight of the month of April.

The electrical scheme has been approved by the electrical supplier company. CHESSE SETUP system, as an electrical power producer, must be reported to the supplier company and it must validate the new installation. CHESSE SETUP system will not connect to the electric provider's net, so the sports center will consume all the electric energy produced.

The final works will be developed jointly with the start-up task carried out by WATTIA.

- Final works (18% Accomplished)

The Final works task includes all the works pending to finish the rest of the tasks. Following a works summary is shown classified which are finished, which are in progress and which are pending to start.

Most of the works pending will be carried out in parallel of the Start Up project phase.

In progress

- Foot bridge on the roof
- Pipes isolation
- Sealing test of the roof
- Installation of air conditioning tubes of the court.

Pending

- Enclosure of the TEST room
- Electrical and monitoring test

Incidents / delays

The complications in the execution of the works due to the redesign of the deposit have been overcome during these two months. As mentioned in previous reports, this redesign produced restrictions during the development of unwanted jobs.

Fortunately, these complications have been left behind and most of the tasks have been carried out within the forecasts.

No new unforeseen events are anticipated beyond those that may appear during the configuration of the installation and last-minute requests from the electricity supplier company.

During the last week of April, it is expected to complete all the tasks of the project except for the final works that must be executed, mostly, together with the set-up of the installation.

Other observations

In April, a new national law for electric self-consumption was approved, it seems that it will not affect the project, but it will depend on the interpretation of the law made by the electricity supplier company. Due to that, the uncertainty is still there because this regulation must be applied, and the electricity supplier company must validate our project.

Because everything is new and must be interpreted by the electric company, some problems may appear. Continuous communication is carried out with the technical electricity supplier company to minimize any risk.

Photographs of the works

- Roof reinforce and structure

Ladder to access the roof

- Tank construction

TEST

TEST isolation

- PV-T panels installation

Hybrid panels installed

- Hydraulic installation

Pumps and hydraulic collectors before and after isolated.

- Elect. And monitoring installation

Control cabinet

Electrical cabinet

- Final Works

Installation of air conditioning tubes of the court

Replacement of the enclosure used as a material entry way

3.7. June 2019 progress report

Tasks performed

The works have officially ended during the last week of June. On June 28, the provisional reception certificate was signed by the construction company, the Director of the Work, the Health and Safety Coordinator and the City Council of Sant Cugat del Vallès.

All the tasks in which the works were split have ended except for the task corresponding to the final works. This task includes all those pending issues to be executed for a good completion of the works, but which don't prevent the start-up of the installation, but which are finishing works.

The pending works according to the provisional reception certificate are:

- Enclosure of the roof of the access hall to the room where the TEST is located.
- Installation of metal visor to prevent the access of rainwater in the room where the electrical connection is located.
- Review of the steps of the access staircase to the room where the TEST is located.
- Review of the footbridge of the roof.
- Electrical connection of 2 lamps of the access corridor of the TEST.
- Delivery the as built plans of the new installation.
- Cleaning and removal of construction material.

Unfortunately, the works have been suspended due to the need to use the sports facilities on the International Roller Games that are being held. During the last week of July these works will be resumed, and they will no longer than two weeks.

The start-up task (Task 5.3.3) started during the month of May and is expected to end during the month of July according to the forecasts of Wattia (responsible for the task).

Summary of the tasks done along the project:

- Roof reinforce and structure (100 % Accomplished)
- Tank construction (100 % Accomplished)

- PV-T panels installation (100% Accomplished)
- Hydraulic installation (100% Accomplished)
- Elect. And monitoring installation (100% Accomplished)
- Final works (70% Accomplished)

Incidents / delays

The Construction Phase (Task 5.3.2) has been longer than expected at the beginning of the task. Several issues have promoted the delay of the works, those issues have been:

- Redesign of the form of the TEST, circular instead of square. It means time to draw new construction plans and to redesign the installation.
- The asbestos pipe found in the basement of the TEST. Due to the safety of the workers, the process had been hand made. No special machinery has been used in the basement task. The result of this less efficient process has been a delay of the task.
- The new national regulation of energy production from renewable sources approved during the project. Since it has not been adapted and well known by the administration and by the rest of the interested parties, time has run and has been lost.
- The authorization of the electric provider. Before starting the new installation, the electrical connection to the electrical network must be approved by the manager of the electrical network. Because each kWh produced by the new installation is one kWh not consumed from the production of the electrical supplier. Obviously, the company has no incentive to approve the new installation and this procedure takes a long time.
- One of the objectives of the construction phase was not to interfere with the use of sports facilities. The works have adapted to the sports calendar and, sometimes, the planning of the construction has also been adapted and delayed.
- Each project change caused by the above issues must be approved by the municipality. As a public administration, the control rules are very restrictive and the procedure for approving the changes are slow and tedious.

Other observations

The main fact to be mentioned is the economic deviation of the works with respect to the original project. Initially, the project was presupposed for an amount of € 821,214.39 (including VAT) while the final economical settlement has been € 953,101.66 (including VAT). It represents a deviation of 16.06%

The start-up begun a month and a half ago, the task is sufficiently worked so that no new temporary and / or economic deviations are foreseen.

Photographs of the works

- Roof reinforce and structure process.

- Tank construction process

- PV-T panels installation process

- Hydraulic installation process

- Elect. And monitoring installation process

4. Corby Pilot Progress Report

Following is the activity summary of the implementation of the Corby Pilot.

4.1. December 2018 progress report

Tasks performed

- Sub structure works to the first four Plots 44 – 47 are almost complete including the Earth Energy Bank installation and along with service ducting to each plot for the varying services of Fiber, Electric and Water.
- All main drainage works to support the first four homes and others is completed and installed under the new driveway to the rear of Plots 44 – 47.
- Setting out of the next 6 Plots 1 – 6 is now completed with the digging of the foundations imminent during Wc 21-01-2018.
- Block and Beam floor are completed to first four Plots 44 – 47 and the perimeter of the footprint has been re filled and compacted with a material to allow for the safe erection of the scaffolding when required.

Incidents / delays

- No significant incidents or issues to report.
- Minor delay to secure footpath closure to accommodate drainage works

Other observations

- First modular wall panels on route to site ready for erection of panels during January.
- Time-lapse camera due to be installed January to record progress and provide online access to view
- The new owners of the Glendale Ecohomes project, etopia Developments, have been getting full involved in the on-going progress. The development scheme will shortly be re-named etopia Corby and will no longer be known as Glendale Ecohomes
- Etopia are also conducting a further review and revision of the program to ensure it meets the required timescales provisionally agreed with CHESS-SETUP consortium on 5th Dec 2018. An update will be issued in January 2019.

Photographs of the works

Image of overall Priors Hall Park site which has been the subject of Administration in 2017 as referenced above

4.2. January 2019 progress report

Tasks performed

- Sub structure works to the first ten homes (Plots 44 – 47 plus Plots 1-6) are almost complete
- Superstructure has arrived on site ready to commence Plot 44-47
- Earth Energy Bank installation has started in plots 1-3.
- All main drainage works to support the first four homes and others is completed and installed under the new driveway to the rear of Plots 44 – 47.

Incidents / delays

- No significant incidents or issues to report.
- Minor delay to secure footpath closure to accommodate drainage works

Other observations

- Time-lapse camera installed to record progress and provide online access to view
- The new owners of the Glendale Ecohomes project, etopia Developments, have been getting full involved in the on-going progress. The development scheme has been re-named **etopia Corby** and will no longer be known as Glendale Ecohomes

Photographs of the works

Image of overall Priors Hall Park site which has been the subject of Administration in 2017 as referenced above

Sand blinding of EEB on Plot 47

Plots 44-47 Foundations and block and beam flooring nearly complete

4.3. February 2019 progress report

Tasks performed

- Sub structure works to the first ten homes (Plots 44 – 47 plus Plots 1-6) are complete
- Superstructure is advancing well for Plot 44-47 – ground floor structure complete and 1st Floor complete on plots 44 and 45.
- Earth Energy Bank installation complete plots 1-3 and well advanced for Plots 4 - 6.
- Foundations complete for garage to Plot 1
- Final arrangements being made with the home energy management and control systems working with Smart Power Systems. This is also part of the process of ensuring data outputs can be provided during this H6 period.

Incidents / delays

- No significant incidents or issues to report.
- Speed of assembling superstructure slightly slower than intended

Other observations

- Superstructure assembly only delayed by training extra teams so that future plots can be accelerated significantly

Photographs of the works

Image of overall Priors Hall Park site which has been the subject of Administration in 2017 as referenced above

4.4. April 2019 progress report

Tasks performed

- Drainage layout and adoption plan finalized with agreement between Northamptonshire County Council, Corby Borough Council and Urban& Civic (U&C). Up until now this has been a cause for delayed start – see 2.2 below
- Haulage routes for construction traffic site access and spoil removal finalized as below (and attached)

Electric Corby

- Site compound plans approved by Master Developer (U&C)

- Landscape details received for side boundary on main avenue and planting completed (planning permission requirement) – see pictures

- Section 38 Highways Adoption program received, and discussions held with U&C on plans for s.38 adoption of internal road within Glendale (pilot) site area
- Temporary boundary fence has been put in place (see photo) to secure the site in readiness for construction of the compound and sacrificial access roadway as per above compound plan

Incidents / delays

- Delays to final approval of drainage scheme for the pilot site have been caused by disagreements between 2 local government authorities (Northamptonshire County Council and Corby Borough Council) on the version of plans approved.
- This has taken several months of discussion but has now been officially resolved at the beginning of May, removing a condition of our planning permission that effected ground works and therefore our ability to start.
- We have been able to instruct the site groundworks team to recommence site compound works which had to pause almost as soon as they had started because the above drainage issue emerged.

Other observations

- While the drainage issue was resolved the opportunity has been taken to visit other installations of the EEB system (Earth Energy Bank) that is to be used in the pilot. This is for the groundwork team to see and learn first-hand how the installation needs to take place. See Photo's below

Photographs of the works

Site temporary boundary fence installed

New dropped kerb for pedestrian crossing installed and utilities manhole height adjusted for new levels. Trees planted in line with landscape plan.

Site visits to other Earth E

4.5. May 2018 progress report

Tasks performed

- Sacrificial access road started
- Plot marking out begun for new homes
- First foundations started
- Preparation for first Earth Energy Bank begun with site inspection of ground conditions
- Site compound plans amended based on need to accommodate compression of the build program and earlier start of the apartment site. The compound was original planned to be temporarily where the apartments would later be built. See original (left) and amended compound location below

Incidents / delays

- Apart from national Bank Holiday on 28th May no delays

Other observations

- On-going review of schedule to identify any and all opportunities to reclaim time lost prior to commencement on site. Adjustment to site compound location part of this process.

Photographs of the works

Work started on sacrificial site access road (red dotted route on site compound plan above)

First plot foundations marked out and trenching work started ready for concrete and EEB (Earth Energy Bank) core work

Zero Carbon Solution (EEB) team and Hawkes (groundworks contractor) inspecting ground conditions

4.6. November 2019 progress report

Tasks performed

- Construction of the first 7 homes is complete (Plots 44-47 and Plots 1-6)
- Data transfer started in the summer and work is on-going with project partners to ensure additional and data integrity is secured as each plot comes online.
- Development of App integration between MasterTherm (heat pump) and SPS (battery and Energy Management unit) finalizing for home occupants
- Sub structure works including installation of the Earth Energy Bank heat storage is now substantially complete for the first 25 homes with all 25 due to be complete by the third week of November i.e. Earth Energy Bank installation complete Plots 44-47 and Plots 1-21
- Work on the foundations for Plot 22 – the 26 plots in total – has started
- Full energy system installation and commission, including heat pumps, MVHR and SHERMS (Smart Home Energy Management that includes 5,5kw battery) completed for first 7 homes
- Sub structure works to the first ten homes (Plots 44 – 47 plus Plots 1-6) are complete
- Dissemination work has involved ongoing social media promotion of the CHESSE-SETUP project but specifically has included TV, radio and print media coverage of the scheme
 - .1. [ITV Tonight](#) program 5th September 2019
 - .2. [Metro newspaper](#) double page spread in September 2019
 - .3. BBC Radio Northamptonshire in [September 2019](#) and November 2019
 - .4. BBC TV (Look East) 13 November 2019

Incidents / delays

- Plot 22 EEB and foundations was due to be complete by first week of November but was delayed slightly by poor weather conditions (rain). Anticipated end of November
- The integration of energy and control systems – between heat pumps and battery systems in particular – have proved problematic and while the core energy generation and storage functions have continued, the data transfer between devices has been interrupted from time to time.
- The primary fault has been traced to MODBUS data rate issue and an internet connectivity challenge. The latter was supposed to be broadband over fiber from day one but delays by the utility provider meant we started by using a 4G link.
- The latter has been resolved and reliable data upload is in place.
- Cost overruns within the development scheme have also presented a challenge with the cost of installation per plot exceed the original budgets by circa 10%. This has resulted in a negotiation with the developer, Etopia to ensure that the 5 different house types (also with deep thermal monitoring) are prioritized. No further budget

is required / requested but it may mean that monitoring data is available from the 5 house types plus 20 additional homes not 21 while total project spend remains the same

Other observations

- Beyond the general construction management for the scheme, integration of systems and stabilization of data flows has been the most challenging activity. The scheme, and the CHES-SETUP element, has continued to receive significant UK publicity.
- Working with a house builder and ensuring the construction teams, who used to more conventional heating and plumbing installations, to secure correct installation in all properties has proved challenging. Skills training and end user training will be crucial as these installations move from Pilot to full commercial roll-out.
- A key learning and a help going forward for future installation is the development of BIM and Digital Twin arrangements for the design and construction stages. We have used Matterport to map the Corby Pilot to inform and improve the design and installations stages in the final stages of Corby and for future schemes.
- <https://my.matterport.com/show/?m=CLX4LdgdR2R> - construction
- <https://my.matterport.com/show/?m=ysHxKpPSrbN> - complete

Photographs of the works

Image of overall Priors Hall Park site which has been the subject of Administration in 2017 as referenced above

1st Phase of Homes Complete – Plots 44-47 and 1-6

PV-T on 2nd Phase Homes Installed Sept/Oct 2019

Earth Energy Banks installed Plots 7-16 and being installed 17-21 October 2019

BBC TV filming Energy Systems November 2019

